

MEDICAL SCIENCES

INTRAAARTERIL CHEMOTHERAPY IN THE BRANCH OF THE INTERNAL CAROTID ARTERY IN COMBINED TREATMENT OF RECURRENT INTRACRANIAL GLIOBLASTOMAS OF THE BRAIN

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Abstract

Glioblastoma with intracranial involvement poses a serious challenge in the care of cancer patients worldwide. At initial presentation, up to 37% of patients present with a significant intracranial mass effect, accompanied by intracranial hypertension and clinical manifestations due to compression of adjacent brain structures. Glioblastoma is a malignant neuroepithelial brain tumor, predominantly of astrocytic origin, with an aggressive course and an extremely poor prognosis. Glioblastoma multiforme (GBM) is the most common and most aggressive form of brain tumor, accounting for up to 52% of primary brain tumors and up to 20% of all intracranial tumors. Despite being the most common primary brain tumor, glioblastoma accounts for only 2-3 cases per 100,000 people in Europe and North America.

According to various literature data, the median overall survival for glioblastoma is no more than 12-15 months after comprehensive treatment, including surgery, radiation therapy, and chemotherapy. This necessitates the development of a personalized approach to the diagnosis and treatment of glioblastomas. Most diagnostic and treatment options for primary or recurrent glioblastoma of the brain involve radical radiation therapy with simultaneous and/or combined alkylating agents, such as temozolamide. However, in the absence of a clinically significant effect and recurrent glioblastomas, drug therapy is very limited in its diversity and does not produce a significant therapeutic effect. According to various authors, the sensitivity of glioblastomas to treatment at the initial presentation and in relapse varies greatly, and this also affects prognosis [1, 2, 5].

The limited treatment options for recurrent glioblastomas drive clinical searches for new, minimally invasive solutions to this problem in modern oncology [5].

Keywords: intra-arterial chemoinfusion into a branch of the internal carotid artery, targeted therapy for recurrent glioblastomas, intracranial metastases.

Purpose of the study:

The aim of the study was to evaluate the immediate results of intra-arterial chemoinfusion into the internal carotid artery in recurrent intracranial glioblastomas in combination with targeted therapy.

Materials and Methods: We studied the immediate and long-term outcomes of patients treated with a

combination of intra-arterial chemoinfusion into the internal carotid artery branch and targeted therapy. A total of 18 patients were enrolled in treatment for recurrent glioblastoma between 2021 and 2023. The combination of intra-arterial chemoinfusion into the internal carotid artery branch and topoisomerase I inhibitors

(irinotecan) at a calculated dose of 100 mg/m² was used.

All patients were classified by gender, tumor morphological type (glioblastoma in 100% of cases), and the nature of the recurrent tumor process: there were 10 men (55%) and 8 women (45%), respectively. All patients had histologically verified (glioblastoma G I and G II) or radiologically confirmed stage III glioblastoma with intracranial location. The frequency and interval of procedures for both intra-arterial chemoinfusion and systemic administration of the targeted agent was 3 weeks. The patients' somatic status at the start of treatment corresponded to an ECOG score of 2-3 and a Karnofsky score of 70-80%. According to our data, intracerebral hypertension syndrome resolved in 16 patients (88%) after the first course of VACP+ targeted therapy, and seizure alertness decreased by 50% or more in 17 patients (94%). Complications included a transient increase in body temperature, local discomfort, and post-embolic syndrome, manifested by severe headaches and a slight decrease in visual acuity. This syndrome was observed in 5 patients (27%) and resolved by the fourth day of inpatient observation.

Results and discussion:

According to the analysis, follow-up tests, and examinations, clinically and statistically significant results were achieved in all 18 cases after 2 or 3 courses. For example, of the 18 patients who completed 6

courses of intra-arterial chemoinfusion into the internal carotid artery in combination with targeted therapy with Bevacizumab at a calculated dose of 7.5 mg/kg, 12 (66%) demonstrated tumor stabilization with improvements. Six (33%) patients demonstrated partial regression of the recurrent tumor. Subsequently, systemic targeted therapy was continued for up to eight courses. According to observations by foreign authors, the therapeutic response to systemic chemotargeted treatment in a number of observations. The median overall survival for glioblastoma, according to various literary data, is 14.6 months after complex treatment, including a combination of surgical treatment, radiation therapy and chemotherapy, which dictates the need to develop a personalized approach to the diagnosis and treatment of glioblastomas [5,6,8]. Subsequently, 11 (61%) of the 12 patients who had previously demonstrated tumor stabilization with positive dynamics experienced progression with continued growth after 8-9 months. Thus, the median event-free survival in this cohort of patients was 16-18 months. In 3 (16%) patients, continued growth was observed after 10 months, and in 4 (22%) patients, this value was 5 months.

We present several cases of complete tumor resection, as well as the formation of a capsule with a necrotic zone using this technique. Below are cases of radiological monitoring and confirmation of the process.

Pic. 1 – MRI signs of SPO - removal of the lesion. Continued growth of the lesion in the temporal lobe of the left hemisphere. Pronounced area of perivocal edema and compression of the posterior horn of the left lateral ventricle. Angioencephalopathy

Pic. 2 – MRI signs of SPO - removal of an intracerebral tumor in the projection of the left temporal lobe. MRI signs of continued growth of the tumor in the left temporal lobe of the brain. Over time, there is a subtle decrease in perifocal edema and mass effect.

Pic. 3 – MRI signs of SPO - removal of an intracerebral tumor in the projection of the left temporal lobe. MRI signs of continued growth of the tumor in the left temporal lobe of the brain, with partial regression noted over time.

Conclusions: Thus, combining targeted therapy with intra-arteriole chemoinfusion into a branch of the internal carotid artery demonstrates a statistically significant effect on tumor progression, increasing drug bioavailability at the tumor site and significantly increasing relapse-free and event-free survival. As a minimally invasive and highly effective technique, these approaches are recommended due to their low rate of postoperative complications, minimal hospital stay, maintaining a satisfactory quality of life, and complete control of recurrent malignancy. The absence of mass effect with our technique allows us to confirm the absence of seizures, which in turn reduces the risk of fatal complications from the underlying oncological process.

References:

1. Brandes A. A., Bartolotti M., Franceschi E. Second surgery for recurrent glioblastoma: advantages

and pitfalls. *Expert Rev Anticancer Ther* 2013 May;13(5):583–7.

2. Chinot O. L., Wick W., Mason W. et al. Bevacizumab plus radiotherapy temozolomide for newly diagnosed glioblastoma. *N Engl J Med*. 2014;370(8):709–22.

3. . Lai A., Tran A., Nghiemphu P. L. et al. Phase II study of bevacizumab plus temozolomide during and after radiation therapy for patients with newly diagnosed glioblastoma multiforme. *J Clin Oncol* 2011 Jan 10;29(2):142–8.

4. 5. Lamborn K. R., Yung W. K., Chang S. M. et al.; North American Brain Tumor Consortium. Progression-free survival: an important end point in evaluating therapy for recurrent high-grade gliomas. *Neuro Oncol* 2008 Apr;10(2):162–70.

5. Oppenlander M. E., Wolf A. B., Snyder L. A. et al. An extent of resection threshold for recurrent glioblastoma and its risk for neurological morbidity. *J Neurosurg.* 2014 Apr;120(4):846–53

6. Ruiz-Sánchez D., Calero M. A., Sastre-Heres A. J. et al. Effectiveness of the bevacizumab-irinotecan regimen in the treatment of recurrent glioblastoma multiforme: Comparison with other secondline treatments without this regimen. *Oncol. Lett* 2012 Nov;4(5):1114–8.

7. Stupp R., Hegi M. E., Mason W. P. et al. Effects of radiotherapy with concomitant and adjuvant temozolomide versus radiotherapy alone on survival in glioblastoma in a randomised phase III study: 5-year analysis of the EORTCNCIC trial. *Lancet Oncol* 2009;10:459–66.

8. Wen P. Y., Macdonald D. R., Reardon D. A. et al. Updated response assessment criteria for high-grade gliomas: response assessment in neuro-oncology working group. *J Clin Oncol* 2010;28:1963–72.